

TOP 10 MOST CITED ARTICLES IN OCTOBER 2024

**International Journal of Managing
Value and Supply Chains (IJMVSC)**

ISSN:0976-979X(Online);2230-7966(print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/ijmvsc.html>

**A FUZZY AHP APPROACH FOR SUPPLIER SELECTION PROBLEM:
A CASE STUDY IN A GEAR MOTOR COMPANY**

Mustafa Batuhan AYHAN

Department of Industrial Engineering, Marmara University, Istanbul, TURKEY

ABSTRACT

Supplier selection is one of the most important functions of a purchasing department. Since by deciding the best supplier, companies can save material costs and increase competitive advantage. However this decision becomes complicated in case of multiple suppliers, multiple conflicting criteria, and imprecise parameters. In addition the uncertainty and vagueness of the experts' opinion is the prominent characteristic of the problem. Therefore an extensively used multi criteria decision making tool Fuzzy AHP can be utilized as an approach for supplier selection problem. This paper reveals the application of Fuzzy AHP in a gear motor company determining the best supplier with respect to selected criteria. The contribution of this study is not only the application of the Fuzzy AHP methodology for supplier selection problem, but also releasing a comprehensive literature review of multi criteria decision making problems. In addition by stating the steps of Fuzzy AHP clearly and numerically, this study can be a guide of the methodology to be implemented to other multiple criteria decision making problems.

KEYWORDS

Supplier Selection, Fuzzy AHP, Multi Criteria Decision Making.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/papers/4313ijmvsc02.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/vol4.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Krajewski, L.J., and Ritzman, L.P., (1996) *Operations Management Strategy and Analysis*. Addison-Wesley Publishing Co., London, UK.
- [2] Ghodsypour, S.H., and O'Brien, C., (1998) —A Decision Support System for Supplier Selection Using an Integrated Analytic Hierarchy Process and Linear Programming, *International Journal of Production Economics*, Vol.56-57(20), 199-212.
- [3] Önüt, S., Kara, S.S., and Işık, E., (2009) —Long Term Supplier Selection Using a Combined Fuzzy MCDM Approach: A Case Study for a Telecommunication Company, *Expert Systems with Applications* Vol. 36(2), 3887-3895. *International Journal of Managing Value and Supply Chains (IJMVSC)* Vol.4, No. 3, September 2013 22
- [4] Liao, C.N., and Kao, H.P., (2011) —An Integrated Fuzzy TOPSIS and MCGP Approach to Supplier Selection in Supply Chain Management, *Expert Systems with Application* Vol.38(9),10803-10811.
- [5] Kilic, H.S., (2013) —An integrated approach for supplier selection in multi item/multi supplier environment, *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, Vol.37(14-15), 7752-7763.
- [6] Xia, W. and Wu, Z., (2007) —Supplier selection with multiple criteria in volume discount environments, *Omega*, Vol.35(5), 494-504.
- [7] Demirtas, E.A., and Üstün, O., (2009) —Analytic Network Process and Multi Period Goal Programming Integration in Purchasing Decisions, *Computers & Industrial Engineering* Vol.56(2), 677-690.
- [8] Dickson, G.W., (1966) —An Analysis of Vendor Selection Systems and Decision, *Journal of Purchasing* Vol.2(1), 5-17.
- [9] Jolai, F., Yazdian, S.A., Shahanaghi, K., and Khojasteh, M.A., (2011) —Integrating Fuzzy TOPSIS and Multi Period Goal Programming for Purchasing Multiple Products From Multiple Suppliers, *Journal of Purchasing & Supply Management*, Vol.17(1), 42-53.
- [10] Weber, C.A., Current J.R. and Benton, W.C. (1991) —Vendor Selection Criteria and Methods, *European Journal of Operational Research* Vol.50(1), 2-18.
- [11] De Boer, L., Labro, E. and Morlacchi, P., (2001) —A Review of Methods Supporting Suppliers Selection, *European Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management* Vol.7(2), 75-89.
- [12] Boran, F.E., Genç, S., Kurt, M., and Akay, D., (2009) —A Multi Criteria Intuitionistic Fuzzy Group Decision Making for Supplier Selection with TOPSIS Method, *Expert Systems with Applications* Vol.36 (8), 11363-11368.
- [13] Sanayei, A., Mousavi, S.F. and Yazdankhak, A., (2010) —Group Decision Making Process for Suppliers Selection with VIKOR Under Fuzzy Environment, *Expert Systems with Applications* Vol. 37 (1), 24-30.
- [14] Ayhan, M.B. (2013). Fuzzy Topsis application for supplier selection problem. *International Journal of Information, Business and Management*, Vol.5(2), 159-174.
- [15] Cheraghi, S.H., Dadashzadeh, M., & Subramanian, M., (2004) —Critical success factors for supplier selection: An Update, *Journal of Applied Business Research*, Vol.20(2), 91–108.
- [16] Arıkan, F., (2013) —An interactive solution approach for multiple objective supplier selection problem with fuzzy parameters, *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, DOI:10.1007/s10845-013-0782-6.

- [17] Wang, J.W., Cheng, C.H., and Cheng, H.K., (2009) —Fuzzy Hierarchical TOPSIS for Supplier Selection, *Applied Soft Computing* 9(1), 377-386.
- [18] Saaty, T.L., (1980) *The Analytic Hierarchy Process*, McGraw-Hill, New York, USA.
- [19] Yahya, S. and Kingsman, B., (1999) —Vendor Rating for an Entrepreneur Development Programme: A Case Study Using the Analytic Hierarchy Process Method, *Journal of the Operational Research Society* Vol.50:916-930.
- [20] Zadeh, L.A., (1965) —Fuzzy Sets, *Information and Control* Vol.8(3), 199-249.
- [21] Cheng, C.H., (1997) —Evaluating Naval Tactical Missile System by Fuzzy AHP Based on the Grade Value of Membership Function, *European Journal of Operational Research* Vol.96(2), 343-350.
- [22] Cheng, C.H., Yang, L.L., and Hwang, C.L., (1999) —Evaluating Attack Helicopter by AHP Based on Linguistic Variable Weight, *European Journal of Operational Research*, Vol. 116(2), 423-435.
- [23] Ruoning, X. and Xiaoyan, Z., (1992) —Extensions of the Analytic Hierarchy Process in Fuzzy Environment, *Fuzzy Sets and System* Vol.52(3), 251-257.
- [24] Petkovic, J., Sevarac, Z., Jaksic, M.L., Marinkovic, S., (2012) —Application of fuzzy AHP method for choosing a technology within service company, *Technics Technologies Education Management*, Vol.7(1), 332-341
- [25] Hwang, C.L., and Yoon, K., (1981) *Multiple Attribute Decision Making Methods and Applications: A State of the Art Survey*, Springer-Verlag, USA.
- [26] Chen, C.T., Lin, C.T., and Huang S.F., (2006) —A Fuzzy Approach for Supplier Evaluation and Selection in Supply Chain Management, *International Journal of Production Economics*, Vol.102(2), 289-301.
- [27] Benayoun, R., Roy, B., and Sussman, B., (1966) ELECTRE: Une méthode pour guider le choix en présence de points de vue multiples. Note de travail 49, SEMA-METRA international, directions scientifique.

Green Supply Chain Management: A Review And Research Direction

Noor Aslinda Abu Seman¹, Norhayati Zakuan¹, Ahmad Jusoh¹,
.Muhamad Zameri Mat Saman² and Mohd Shoki Md Arif

¹ Faculty of Management and Human Resource Development, Universiti Teknologi
Malaysia, 81310, UTM Skudai Malaysia ² Faculty of Mechanical, Universiti Teknologi
Malaysia, 81310, UTM Skudai Malaysia

ABSTRACT

Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM) has appeared as an environmental innovation which integrates environmental concerns into supply chain management. GSCM has gained popularity with both academic and practitioners. The purpose of the paper is to briefly review the recent literatures of the GSCM and also determine the new direction area of this emerging field. A detailed review is used to sort out the literature and develop the research direction of the study. The review is focused on development of GSCM in a developed and developing countries including all those researchers which is relevant to environmental and social sustainability towards operation management and the supply chain. It shows that lack of researches to examine the adoption and implementation of GSCM practices especially in developing countries such as Malaysia. Thus, the authors bring forward a proposed research direction on GSCM adoption and implementation in Malaysia's manufacturing industries.

KEYWORDS

Supplier Selection, Fuzzy AHP, Multi Criteria Decision Making.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/papers/3112ijmvsc01.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/vol4.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Shultz, C.J. II & Holbrook, M.B., (1999) – Marketing and Tragedy of the Commons: A Synthesis Commentary and Analysis for Action, *Journal of Public Policy and Marketing*, Vol. 18, No. 2, pp218-29.
- [2] Ninlawan, C., Seksan, P., Tossapol, K., & Pilada, W., (2011) – The Implementation of Green Supply Chain Management Practices in Electronics Industry, *Proceedings of the International Multi-conference of Engineers and Computer Scientists*, 3.
- [3] Zhu, Q. & Sarkis, J., (2004) — Relationships between operational practices and performance among early adopters of green supply chain management practices in Chinese manufacturing enterprises, *Journal of Operations Management*, 22, pp 265-289.
- [4] Beamon, B.M., (1999) — Designing the green supply chain, *Logistics Information Management*, Vol. 12, No. 4, pp 332-342.
- [5] Zhu, Q., Geng, Y., Fujita, T., & Hashimoto, S., (2010) — Green Supply Chain Management in Leading Manufacturers: Case Studies in Japanese Large Companies, *Management Research Review*, Vol. 33, No. 4, pp380-392.
- [6] Fortes, J., (2009) — Green Supply Chain Management: A Literature Review, *Otago Management Graduate Review*, 7, pp51-62.
- [7] Srivastava, S.K., (2007) — Green supply-chain management: a state-of-the-art literature review, *International Journal of Management Reviews*, Vol. 9, No. 1, pp53–80.
- [8] Rao, P. & Holt, D., (2005) — Do green supply chains lead to competitiveness and economic performance?, *International Journal of Operations and Production Management*, Vol. 25, No. 9, pp898–916.
- [9] Zhu, Q. & Sarkis, J., (2006) — An inter-sectoral comparison of green supply chain management in China: drivers and practices, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Vol. 14, No. 5, pp472–86.
- [10] Large, R.O. & Thomsen, C.G., (2011) — Drivers of Green Supply Chain Management Performance: Evidence from Germany, *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, Vol. 17, pp 176-184.
- [11] Azevedo, S.G., Carvalho, H., & Machado, V.C., (2011) – The Influence of Green Practices on Supply Chain Performance: A Case Study Approach, *Transportation Research Part E*, Vol. 47, pp850-871.
- [12] Chiou, T.Y., Chan, H.K., Lettice, F., & Chung, S.H., (2011) – The Influence of Greening the Suppliers and Green Innovation on Environmental Performance and Competitive Advantage in Taiwan, *Transportation Research Part E*, 47, pp 822-836.
- [13] Cagno, E., Guido, M.J.L., Perotti, S., & Zorzini, M., (2011) – The impact of green supply chain practices on company performance: the case of 3PLs, *Lancaster University Management School Working Paper*, pp1-31.
- [14] Arimura, T.H., Darnall, N., Katayama, H., (2011) — Is ISO 14001 a gateway to more advanced voluntary action? The case of green supply chain management, *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 61, pp 170–182.
- [15] Hsu, C.W. & Hu, A.H., (2008) — Green Supply Chain Management in the Electronic Industry, *International Journal Environment Science Technology*, Vol. 5, No. 2, pp205-216.

- [16] Shang, K.C., Lu, C.S., Li, S., (2010) —A taxonomy of green supply chain management capability among electronics-related manufacturing firms in Taiwan, *Journal of Environmental Management*, 91, pp1218–1226.
- [17] Holt, D. & Ghobadian, A., (2009) —An Empirical Study of Green Supply Chain Management Practices among UK Manufacturers, *Journal of Manufacturing Technology*, Vol.20, No.7, pp933-956.
- [18] Nawrocka, D., Brorson, T., & Lindqvist, T., (2009) —ISO 14001 in environmental supply chain practices, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 17, pp1435–1443.
- [19] Lee, S., (2008) —Drivers for the participation of small and medium-sized suppliers in green supply chain initiatives, *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, Vol. 13, No. 3, pp185–198.
- [20] Raymond, P. C., Lopez, J., Marche, S., Perron, G.M., & Wright, R., (2008) —Influences, practices and opportunities for environmental supply chain management in Nova Scotia SMEs, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 16, pp1561–1570.
- [21] Chen, Y., (2008) —The Driver of Green Innovation and Green Image – Green Core Competence, *Journal of Business Ethics*, 81, pp531–543.
- [22] Chien, M. K. & Shih, L. H., (2007) —An empirical study of the implementation of green supply chain management practices in the electrical and electronic industry and their relation to organizational performances, *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Tech.*, Vol.4, No.3, pp 383-394.
- [23] Simpson, D., Power, D. & Samson, D., (2007) —Greening the automotive supply chain: a relationship perspective, *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 27, No.1, pp 28-48.
- [24] Vachon, S. & Klassen, R.D., (2006) —Extending green practices across the supply chain: the impact of upstream and downstream integration, *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 26, No.7, pp 795-821.
- [25] Anbumozhi, V. & Kanada, Y., (2005) —Greening the production and supply chains in Asia: is there a role for voluntarily initiatives?, IGES Kansai Research Center Discussion Paper, KRC2005, No.6E. Available online: <http://www.iges.or.jp>

ISSUES AND CHALLENGES IN THE SUPPLY CHAIN OF FRUITS & VEGETABLES SECTOR IN INDIA: A REVIEW

Saurav Negi¹ and Neeraj Anand²

¹ Doctoral Research Fellow, Centre for Continuing Education, University of Petroleum and Energy Studies, Dehradun, India ² Professor and Head (LSCM & Operations), College of Management and Economic Studies, University of Petroleum and Energy Studies, Dehradun, India

ABSTRACT

Research limitations/implications- The authors have focuses only on Fruits and Vegetables sector, authors may look at other sector like food processing unit, cold chain and other perishable items such as meat, dairy industry, chocolate, beverages etc. Practical implications- Overcoming

these issues and challenges will benefit the decision makers and various stakeholders like the farmers, state government, transporters and food processing unit to understand the current status, issues and challenges for better planning and management in the field of fruits and vegetables supply chain. Originality/value- Most of the prior literature have been focused on the general issues like cold chain, marketing efficiency etc. of fruit and vegetables supply chain. There exists a need of having review on supply chain specifically in F&V sector, identifying all the factors affecting it and suggest mitigation strategies. This review fill this gap in the literature of supply chain management of Fruits and Vegetables sector. International Journal of Managing Value and Supply Chains (IJMVSC) Vol. 6, No. 2, June 2015 48

Keywords

Fruits & Vegetables, Supply Chain Management, Inefficiency, Infrastructure, Wastage

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/papers/6215ijmvsc05.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/vol6.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] ASSOCHAM. (2013). Horticulture Sector in India- State level experience. New Delhi: TheAssociatedChamberof Commerce and IndustryofIndia.
- [2] Bhardwaj, S., &Palaparthi, I. (2008). Factors Influencing Indian Supply Chains of of Fruits andVegetables: A Literature Review. The Icfai University Journal of Supply Chain Management, V (3),59-68.
- [3] Blackburn, J., & Scudder, G. (2009). Supply chain strategies for perishable products: the case offreshproduce. Productionand OperationsManagement, 18(2), 129-137.
- [4] Dharni, K., & Sharma, S. (2008). Food Processing in India: Opportunities and Constraints. TheIcfai UniversityJournalofAgriculturalEconomics, V(3), 30-38.
- [5] FICCI. (2010). BOTTLENECKS IN INDIAN FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY. RetrievedJanuary22,2014,fromFICCIWebsite:<http://www.ficci.com/SEDocument/20073/Food-ProcessingBottlenecks-study.pdf>
- [6] GOI.(2012).NationalFoodProcessingpolicy.Retrieved1124,2012,fromConfederationofWomenEntrepreneurs:<http://co-we.com/wp-content/uploads/national-food-processing-policy.pdf>
- [7] Halder, P., &Pati, S. (2011). A Need For Paradigm Shift to Improve Supply Chain ManagementofFruits&Vegetablesin India.AsianJournal of Agricultureand Rural Development,1 (1),1-20.
- [8] Jain,N.(2007,810-12).InternationalConferenceonAgribusinessandFoodIndustryinDeveloping Countries :Opportunities and Challenges. Retrieved 1 22, 2014, from IIM lucknow:http://www.iiml.ac.in/events/P1_02_Neeraj_Jain.pdf
- [9] Kapoor,P.(2009,July28).Doctoc-InternationalSummitonFoodProcessingandAgribusiness.Retrieved January 22, 2014, from Docstoc.com:<http://www.docstoc.com/docs/127265667/ENTREPRENEURIAL-OPPORTUNITIES-IN-THEAGRI-BUSINESS>
- [10] KPMG,&ASSOCHAM.(2009).FoodprocessingandAgribusiness.RetrievedJanuary22,2014, from Smallb.in A SIDBI Initiative:http://smallb.in/sites/default/files/knowledge_base/reports/FoodProcessingandAgribusinessAssocham_opt.pdf
- [11] Mathi,K.M.(2007,August10-12).InternationalConferenceonAgribusinessandFoodIndustry in Developing Countries: Opportunities and Challenges. Retrieved January 22, 2014, fromIIMLucknowWebsites:http://www.iiml.ac.in/events/C9_01_K_Malar_Mathi.pdf
- [12] Modi,P.,Mishra,D.,Gulati,H.,&Murugesan,K.(2009).UTTARAKHANDSTATECOOPERATIVE FEDERATION: CAN IT HELP THE HORTICULTURE FARMERS? VISION—TheJournalof BusinessPerspective, 13 (2), 53-61.
- [13] MOSPI. (2013). State Domestic Product and other aggregates. Retrieved April 29, 2014, fromMinistry of Statistics and ProgrammeImplementation:http://mospi.nic.in/Mospi_New/site/inner.aspx?status=3&menu_id=82
- [14] Murthy, D. S., Gajanana, T. M., Sudha, M., &Dakshinamoorthy, V. (2009). Marketing andPostharvestlossesinfruits:ItsimplicationsonAvailabilityandeconomy.IndianJournalofAgricultural economics, 64(2), 259-275.

- [15] Naidu, S. (2007, August 10-12). International Conference on Agribusiness and Food Industry in Developing Countries: Opportunities and Challenges. Retrieved January 22, 2014, from IIM Lucknow Website: <http://www.iiml.ac.in/events/ICABFI.htm>
- [16] Narula, S.A. (2011). Reinventing cold chain industry in India: need of the hour. Interview with Mr Sanjay Aggarwal. Journal of Agribusiness in Developing and Emerging Economies, 1 (2).
- [17] NHB. (2013). Area and Production Statistics. Retrieved February 4, 2014, from National Horticulture Board: <http://nhb.gov.in/area%20production.html>
- [18] NHB. (2015). Area and Production Status- Final Area & Production Estimates for Horticulture Crops for 2013-2014. Retrieved January 26, 2015, from National Horticulture Board: <http://nhb.gov.in/area%20production.html>
- [19] POLICY, N. F. (n.d.). Retrieved 11 24, 2012, from <http://co-we.com/wp-content/uploads/nationalfood-processing-policy.pdf>
- [20] Ramesh, S. (2009, July 28). Food Processing Sector in India-Challenges and Opportunities-KPMG. Retrieved January 22, 2014, from Scribd.com: <http://www.scribd.com/doc/39050239/Food-Processing-Opportunities-in-India-Ppt>
- [21] Rathore, J., Sharma, A., & Saxena, K. (2010). Cold Chain Infrastructure for Frozen Food: A Weak Link in Indian Retail Sector. The IUP Journal of Supply Chain Management, VII (1 & 2), 90-103.
- [22] Salin, V. (1998). Information technology in agri-food supply chains. International Food and Agribusiness Management Review, 1 (3), 329-34.
- [23] Satyanarayana, A., Math, R.G., Jyothirmayi, T., & Rao, D.G. (2007, August 10-12). International Conference on Agribusiness and Food Industry in Developing Countries: Opportunities and Challenges. Retrieved January 22, 2014, from IIM Lucknow website: http://www.iiml.ac.in/events/C5_03_A_Satyanarayana.pdf
- [24] Sharma, G., & Singh, S. (2011). Economic Analysis of Post-harvest Losses in Marketing of Vegetables in Uttarakhand. Agricultural Economics Research Review, 24, 309-315.
- [25] Shukla, D. (2010, February 15-16). UNCTAD. Retrieved January 22, 2014, from Engaging the Trading Community Forum on WTO, Trade Facilitation and the Private Sector in Developing Countries-Trade Obstacles Faced by Indian Exporters: http://unctad.org/sections/wcmu/docs/ettcp05_en.pdf

Application of Fishbone Analysis for Evaluating Supply Chain and Business Process A CASE STUDY ON THE ST JAMES HOSPITAL

Tarun Kanti Bose

Assistant Professor, Business Administration Discipline, Khulna University, Khulna 9208, Bangladesh

ABSTRACT

Conducting business is certainly not the easiest thing to do in this hyper-competitive business fraternity. The scenario for the manufacturing firms is even more challenging as their value chain is the longest and widest by every consideration. Therefore, it is immensely vital for the manufacturing operators to analyze their supply chain properly so that they can establish a real good one in their armoury. The fishbone analysis is a tool for analyzing the business process and its effectiveness. It is also commonly referred to as the Ishikawa Diagram because it was invented and incorporated by Mr. Kaoru Ishikawa, a Japanese quality control statistician. It is defined as a fishbone because of its structural outlook and appearance. The fishbone analysis is a tool for analyzing the business process and its effectiveness. This study was intended towards evaluating the supply chain and business process of St. James Hospital. The analysis reveals that the problem areas are lack of proper equipment, faulty process, misdirected people, poorly managed materials, improper environment, and inefficient management.

KEYWORDS

Fishbone, St James Hospital, Business Process, Supply Chain

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/papers/3212ijmvsc02.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/vol3.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] American Society for Quality (2005), Fishbone diagram Accessed From: <http://www.asq.org/learn-about-quality/cause-analysis-tools/overview/fishbone.html> Accessed by: March 2, 2011.
- [2] Balanced Scorecard Institute (2007), Basic tools for process improvement, Module 5– Cause and Effect diagram, Accessed From: <http://www.balancedscorecard.org/files/c-eddiag.pdf>, Accessed by: March 2, 2011.
- [3] Bence, V (1995), ST. James Hospital and Lucas Engineering System Ltd.-A Public/Private Sector Collaboration in BPR Project B-The Re-organization of Purchasing and Supplies. Cranfield Centre for Logistics and Transportation, Cranfield University. UK.
- [4] Gregory, F.H (1992) Cause, Effect, Efficiency & Soft Systems Models, Journal of the Operational Research Society, 44 (4), pp 333-344.
- [5] Ishikawa, K (1986). Guide to Quality Control. Tokyo, Japan: Asian Productivity Organization.
- [6] Ishikawa, K (1990); Introduction to Quality Control; ISBN 4-906224-61-X OCLC 61341428.
- [7] Otto, K. (1995)—Course Notes on Design for Assembly, MIT Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- [8] Poli, C., Graves, J., and Sunderland, J.E. (1988) Computer-Aided Product Design for Economical Manufacture. ASME Computers in Engineering, 1(4), pp. 23-37.
- [9] Public Health Infrastructure (2008), Fishbone (Ishikawa) Diagram (Example), Accessed From: <http://www.phf.org/infras.html>, Accessed by: March 4, 2011.
- [10] Ruhm, K. H (2004) Cause and Effect Diagram, Internet Portal "Measurement Science and Technology"; Retrieved from: www.mmm.ethz.ch/dok01/d0000538.pdf, Accessed by: March 5, 2011.
- [11] Southern, G (1995), Business Change and Re-engineering: A Brainstorming Approach, Journal of Corporate Transformation, 2(1), p.40.
- [12] Straker, D. (2010) Cause-Effect Diagram. Retrieved from: Quality Tools: http://syque.com/quality_tools/toolbook/cause-effect/cause-effect.htm, Accessed by: March 4, 2011.
- [13] Sturges, R., and Kilani, M. (1992) Towards an Integrated Design for an Assembly Evaluation and Reasoning System. Computer-Aided Design, 24(2), pp. 67-78.
- [14] U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (1993) "Life-Cycle Assessment: Inventory Guidelines and Principles", EPA Report No. EPA/600/R-92/245, Office of Research and Development, Washington, D.C.
- [15] Watson, G. (2004). The Legacy of Ishikawa. Quality Progress, 37(4), pp. 54-47.

AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH FOR E-GOVERNMENT TRANSFORMATION

Ali M. Al-Khouri

Emirates Identity Authority, Abu Dhabi, UAE

ABSTRACT

Despite the immeasurable investment in e-government initiatives throughout the world, such initiatives have yet to succeed in fully meeting expectations and desired outcomes. A key objective of this research article is to support the government of the UAE in realizing its vision of e-government transformation. It presents an innovative framework to support e-government implementation, which was developed from a practitioner's perspective and based on learnings from numerous e-government practices around the globe. The framework presents an approach to guide governments worldwide, and UAE in particular, to develop a top down strategy and leverage technology in order to realize its long term goal of e-government transformation. The study also outlines the potential role of modern national identity schemes in enabling the transformation of traditional identities into digital identities. The work presented in this study is envisaged to help bridge the gap between policy makers and implementers, by providing greater clarity and reducing misalignment on key elements of e-government transformation. In the hands of leaders that have a strong will to invest in e-government transformation, the work presented in this study is envisaged to become a powerful tool to communicate and coordinate initiatives, and provide a clear visualization of an integrated approach to e-government transformation.

KEYWORDS

e-Government, Transformation, National ID Schemes.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/papers/2111ijmvsc02.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/vol2.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Atkinson, R.D. and Castro, D. (2008) "Digital Quality of Life," The Information Technology and Innovation Foundation, pp. 137–145.
- [2] Mälkiä, M., Anttiroiko, A. and Savolainen, R. (eds.) (2004) *E-Transformation in Governance: New Directions in Government*. Hershey, PA: Idea Group Publishing.
- [3] Melville, A. (2007) "E-Government and Organisational Transformation: Lessons Learnt from Liverpool and Hertfordshire," *New Local Government Network*. June 7.
- [4] Martin, G. (2009) "Government's Response to Financial Crisis will Change the Role of the Public Sector Around the World," *Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu* [Online]. Available from: https://www.deloitte.com/view/en_G-X/global/press/global-press-releases-en/06ab63ec49101210VgnVCM100000ba42f00aRCR-D.htm. Accessed [4 October 2010].
- [5] OECD (2009) Report on the Impact of Financial Crisis on e-Government in OECD Countries. 5th Ministerial eGovernment Conference, 19-20 November – Malmö, Sweden, Available from: <http://www.oecd.org/dataoecd/57/57/44089570.pdf>.
- [6] Stoica, O. (2010) "Implementing e-government with financial constraints", *The Network of Institutes and Schools of Public Administration in Central and Eastern Europe* [Online]. Available from: http://www.nispa.org/_portal/files/conferences/2010/papers/201004221034060.StoicaOvidiu.doc [Accessed 3 July 2010].
- [7] Lapsley, I. (2010) "New Public Management in the Global Financial Crisis-Dead, Alive, or Born Again?" UK: University of Edinburgh Business School.
- [8] Abhichandani, T. (2008) *Evaluation of E-Government Initiatives for Citizen-Centric Delivery: Analysis of Online Public Transit Information Services*. Germany: VDM Verlag Publishing.
- [9] Chhabra, S. and Kumar, M. (2009) *Integrating E-business Models for Government Solutions: Citizen-Centric Service Oriented Methodologies and Processes*. Hershey, PA, USA: Information Science Reference.
- [10] Hewson, W., Jones, R., Hunter, D. and Meekings, A. (2004) *Towards a Citizen-centric Authority: Beyond CRM, E-Government and the Modernising Agenda in the UK Public Sector*. UK: Hewson Consulting Group.
- [11] Bimber, B. (1999) "The Internet and citizen communication with government: Does the medium matter?" *Political Communication*, Vol. 16, pp. 409-428.
- [12] Curtain, G.G., Sommer, M.H. and Vis-Sommer, V. (2004) *The World of E-Government*. New York: Haworth Press.
- [13] Tubtimhin, J. and Pipe, R. (2009) *Global e-Governance: Advancing e-Governance through Innovation and Leadership, Volume 2 Global E-Governance Series*. IOS Press.
- [14] Mansell, R. (2002) *Inside the Communication Revolution: Evolving Patterns of Social and Technical Interaction*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.

- [15] Wilhelm, A.G. (2004) *Digital Nation: Toward an Inclusive Information Society*. Cambridge,MA:TheMITPress.
- [16] Nixon, P.G., Koutrakou, V.N. and Rawal, R. (eds) (2010) *Understanding E-Government in Europe: Issues and Challenges*. London: Routledge.
- [17] Shapiro, A.L. (1999) *The Control Revolution: How the Internet is Putting Individuals in Charge and Changing the World We Know*. New York:CenturyFoundation.
- [18] Gronlund,A.(2002)*Electronic Government: Design, Applications and Management*. Hershey, PA: Idea Group Publishing.
- [19] Garson,D.G.(1999)*Information Technology and Computer Applications in Public Administration: Issues and Trends*. London: Idea Group Publishing.
- [20] Kamarck, E.C. and Nye, J.S. (eds.) (2002) *Governance.Com: Democracy in the Information Age, Visions of Governance in the 21st Century*. Washington, D.C.: Brookings Institution Press.
- [21] Mittrakas, A., Hengeveld, P., Polemi, D. and Gamper, J. (2007) *Secure E-Government Web Services*. Hershey, PA: Idea Group Publishing.
- [22] Mendes, M.J. and Suomi, R. Passos, C. (eds.) (2004) *Digital Communities in a Networked Society: E-Commerce, E-Business, and E-Government: The Third IFIP Conference on E-Commerce, E-Business, and E-Government*, International Federation for Information Processing (Series), Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- [23] UN (2010) —UN E-government Survey – 2010: Leveraging e-government at a time of financial and economic crisis, UNDESA [Online]. Available from: <http://unpan1.un.org/intradoc/groups/public/documents/un-dpadm/unpan038855.pdf>. [Accessed 2 April 2010].
- [24] UN(2008)"UNE-government Survey–2008: From E-government to Connected Governance", UNDESA [Online]. Available from: <http://unpan1.un.org/intradoc/groups/public/documents/un/un-pan028607.pdf> [Accessed 2 April 2010].
- [25] Layne, K. and Lee, J.W. (2001) —Developing Fully Functional E-Government: A Four Stage Model, *Government Information Quarterly*, vol. 2, pp. 122-36.

**FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMERS' BUYING DECISIONS OF MOBILE
PHONE: A STUDY ON KHULNA CITY, BANGLADESH**

Md Reaz Uddin¹ Nusrat Zahan Lopa² and Md. Oheduzzaman³

**¹ Assistant Professor, Business Administration Discipline, Khulna
University, Bangladesh ² Assistant Professor, Business Administration
Discipline, Khulna University, Bangladesh ³ Independent Researcher, Khulna**

ABSTRACT

Mobile phone has diverse usages to different users in accordance with their necessities. With dramatic increase in mobile phone usage in recent years, people take into account various factors while they decide purchasing a mobile phone. This study has put efforts to uncover the underlying factors those affect customers in choosing mobile phone. Data were collected from those people live in Khulna city maintaining equal ratios of various groups like male, female, businessmen, employees, students and others (mostly housewives). To select desired respondents, convenient sampling method was used. A structured questionnaire designed based on previous study with five point Likert scale was used to interview respondents. Factor analysis was applied to extract the underlying factors affect mobile phone purchasing decision. The results show that the most important factor is physical attributes. Some other factors are pricing, charging and operating facilities, size and weight, friends' and colleagues' recommendations, neighbors' recommendations and advertising.

KEYWORDS

Mobile Phone, Purchasing Decisions, Customer Choice.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/papers/5214iimvsc03.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/vol5.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Batra, R and Ahtola, OT (1990). Measuring the hedonic and utilitarian sources of consumer attitudes, *Marketing Letters*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 159-170.
- [2] Chernev, A (2003). When more is less and less is more: The role of ideal point of availability and assortment in consumer choice', *Journal of Consumer Research*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 169-184.
- [3] Dorsch, MJ, Grove, SJ and Darden, WR (2000). Consumer intention to use service category, *Journal of Services Marketing*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 92-118.
- [4] In-Stat/MDR (2002). The worldwide PDA market: the next generation of mobile computing, *Research Report*, Accessed 7 August.
- [5] Laroche, M, Kim, C and Matsui, T (2003). Which decision heuristics are used in consideration set formation, *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 192-209.
- [6] Liu, CM (2002). The effects of promotional activities on brand decision in the cellular telephone industry, *The Journal of Product & Brand Management*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 42-51.
- [7] Moorthy, S, Ratchford, B and Talukdar, D (1997). Consumer information search revisited, *Journal of Consumer Research*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 263-277.
- [8] Moschis, GP (1976). Social comparison and informal group influence, *Journal of Marketing Research*, vol. 13, pp. 237-244.
- [9] Requelme, H (2001). Do consumers know what they want?, *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 437-448.
- [10] Swait, J and Adamowicz, W (2001). The influence of task complexity on consumer choice: A latent class model of decision strategy switching, *Journal of Consumer Research*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 135-148.
- [11] Wilska, TA (2003). Mobile phone use as part of young people's consumption styles, *Journal of Consumer Policy*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 442-464.

**ADOPTING AGILE SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT: ISSUES
AND CHALLENGES**

Hassan Hajjdiab and AlShaima Taleb

**College of Engineering and Computer Science Abu Dhabi University Abu
Dhabi, UAE, P.O. Box 59911**

ABSTRACT

In the recent few years more and more software development organizations are striving to adopt agile software development methods and techniques. Successful agile adoption leads to producing higher quality software, enhanced developer morale and a lower cost than the traditional water wall model approach. However, Agile adoption always comes with special challenges and accordingly, fundamental organizational changes are necessary for successful outcome. The main contribution of this paper is that we present a case study for agile adoption in a government entity in the U.A.E and we compare and analyze the outcomes obtained with other published case studies in this domain.

KEYWORDS

Agile development, Scrum, Agile adoption, waterfall methodology, software engineering, case study, adoption challenges

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/papers/0911mvsc01.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/vol2.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Greg Smith and Ahmed Sidky, *Becoming Agile: ... in an imperfect world*, Manning Publications, 2009.
- [2] Mark Kennaley, *SDLC 3.0: Beyond a Tacit Understanding of Agile*, Fourth Medium Press, 2010.
- [3] GatherSpace Team, "Agile software development," Retrieved January 15, 2011, January 2011.
- [4] Kent Beck, Mike Beedle, Arievan Bennekum, Alistair Cockburn, Ward Cunningham, Martin Fowler, James Grenning, Jim Highsmith, Andrew Hunt, Ron Jeffries, Jon Kern, Brian Marick, Robert C. Martin, Steve Mellor, Ken Schwaber, Jeff Sutherland, and Dave Thomas, —Manifesto for agile software development, 2001.
- [5] John Hunt, *Agile Software Construction*, Springer, September 2005.
- [6] G. Benefield, —Rolling out agile in a large enterprise, in 41st Hawaii International Conference on System Science, 2008, IEEE Computer Society.
- [7] Tore Dyb^o and Torgeir Dingsøy, —Empirical studies of agile software development: A systematic review, in *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 50, pp. 833–859, August 2008.
- [8] Kieran Conboy, Sharon Coyle, Xiaofeng Wang, and Minna Pikkarainen, —People over process: Key challenges in agile development, in *IEEE Software*, vol. 28, pp. 48–57, 2011.
- [9] Jayakanth Srinivasan and Kristina Lundqvist, —Using agile methods in software product development: A case study, in *Information Technology: New Generations*, Third International Conference on, vol. 0, pp. 1415–1420, 2009.
- [10] Mikael Lindvall, Dirk Muthig, Aldo Dagnino, Christina Wallin, Michael Stupperich, David Kiefer, John May, and Tuomo K^hnen, —Agile software development in large organizations, in *Computer*, vol. 37, pp. 26–34, 2004.
- [11] Mike Cohn and Doris Ford, —Introducing an agile process to an organization, in *Computer*, vol. 36, pp. 74–78, 2003.
- [12] M. Cohn, *Succeeding with Agile Software development using scrum*, Addison-Wesley, 2009.
- [13] J. Tabaka, —11 ways agile adoption fails, in *StickyMinds.com Column*, stickyMinds.com, retrieved March 2011.
- [14] A. Atlas, —Accidental adoption: The story of scrum at amazon.com, in *Agile 2009 conference*, Chicago, IL, 2009, pp. 135–140.
- [15] K. Scotland and A. Boutin, —Integrating scrum with the process framework at yahoo! europe, in *Agile 2008 conference*, Toronto, ON, 2008, pp. 191–195.
- [16] G. Cloke, —Get your agile freak on! agile adoption at yahoo! music, in *Proceedings of the AGILE 2007*, Washington, DC, USA, 2007, pp. 240–248, IEEE Computer Society.
- [17] Andrew Begeland Nachiappan Nagappan, —Usage and perceptions of agile software development in an industrial context: An exploratory study, in *Proceedings of the First International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement*, Washington, DC, USA, 2007, ESEM '07, pp. 255–264, IEEE Computer Society.
- [18] B. Greene, —Agile methods applied to embedded firmware development, in *Proceedings of the Agile Development Conference*, Washington, DC, USA, 2004, pp. 71–77, IEEE Computer Society.

The Relationship between Organizational Innovations, Internal Sources of Knowledge and Organizational Performance

Rim Maâlej Ben Zaied¹ and Hanène Louati² and Habib Affes³

¹Research Laboratory in Information Technology, Governance and Entrepreneurship, FSEGS University, Sfax, Tunisia² Research Laboratory in Finance, Governance and Accounting, FSEGS University, Sfax, Tunisia³ Department of Business administration, Jizzan University, Arabia Saoudit

ABSTRACT

This research examines the importance of internal sources of knowledge and its relationship with organizational innovation and organizational performance. We did this research on a sample of 200 Tunisian companies operating in different sectors. Our study was built mainly on the basis of quantitative method. The data collection method is the questionnaire as part of a hypothetical-deductive approach and the mode of administration is self-administered survey and e-mail survey. The empirical verification of the assumptions of this research has led us to confirm the relationship between internal and external sources of knowledge with organizational innovation and organizational performance and to infirm the relationship between organizational innovation and organizational performance.

KEYWORDS

Organizational innovation, internal sources of knowledge, organizational performance

ForMoreDetails:<https://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/papers/6115jmvsc05.pdf>

VolumeLink:<https://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/vol6.html>

REFERENCES

1. Argyris et Schon, D. (1978) *Organizational learning: A theory of action perspective*, Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
2. Bagozzi et Yi Y. (1988) "On the Evaluation of Structural Equations models". *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science* . 74, pp94-16.
3. Bierly et Chakrabarti A. (1996) "Generic knowledge strategies in the U.S. pharmaceutical industry". *Strategic Management Journal* .vol .123,pp135-17.
4. Bohémier, Sophie, (2006) *La performance organisationnelle par l'intégration de l'orientation marché et l'orientation innovation*. Université du Québec A Montréal.
5. Cainelli et al. 2006 "Innovation and economic performance in services: a firm-level analysis", *Cambridge Journal of Economics* .vol. 435, pp458-30.
6. Cameron K. (1986) Effectiveness as paradox: consensus and conflict in conceptions of organizational effectiveness. *Management Science*. Vol.539, pp53-32.
7. Calantone et al. (2002) "Learning orientation firm innovation capability and firm performance", *Industrial Marketing Management* .vol.515,pp524-31.
8. Cassiman B et Venglers R. (2006). "In search of complementarity in the innovation strategy: internal R&D and external knowledge acquisition". *Management Science*, vol.68, pp82-52.
9. Chakravarthy B. (1986) «Measuring strategic performance», *Strategic Management Journal*, vol.437, pp58-7. Chen S et Chen A. (2006). "Knowledge management performance evaluation: a decade review from 1995 to 2004". *Journal of Information Science* , vol.17, pp38-32.
10. Chin W et al. (1996) A Partial Least Squares Latent Variable Modeling Approach for Measuring Interaction Effects: Results from a Monte Carlo Simulation Study and Voice Mail Emotion/Adaptation Study. *Proceedings of the Seventeenth International Conference on Information Systems* 21:41. Cleveland: Ohio.
11. Chiou H et Lin P. (2009) *Principles and Application of Structural Equation*. China: Beijing: China Light Industry Press.
12. Damanpour F et al. (1989) "The relationship between types of innovation and organizational performance". *Journal of Management Studies* ,vol. 587, pp 601-6.
13. Damanpour F et al. (2009). "Combinative effects of innovation types and organizational performance: a longitudinal study of service organizations". *Journal of Management Studies* , vol.650, pp 675-64.
14. Damanpour F et al. (1998) Theories of organizational structure and innovation adoption: the role of environmental change. *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*. vol.1, pp24-15.
15. Dewar R et Dutton J.E. (1986) "The adoption of radical and incremental innovations: An empirical analysis". *Management Science* .vol.1422, pp1433-32.
16. Dozi G. (1998). *Sources, procedures and microeconomic effect of innovation*.
17. Drucker P. (1993) *Au-delà du capitalisme : La métamorphose de cette fin de siècle*., Paris: Dunod.
18. Dubbé C et al. (2012). *L'innovation: définition et concepts*. Québec.
19. Eddleston K. (2008) "Resource configuration in family firms: linking resources, strategic planning and technological opportunities to performance". *Journal of Management Studies*, vol.26, pp50-45.

**EFFECT OF SUPPLIER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT ON
THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN THE
KENYA PUBLIC SECTOR.**

Ondieki John Nyamasege¹ and Oteki Evans Biraori²

**¹ PhD student, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture & Technology,
Nairobi, Kenya. ² PhD student, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture &
Technology, Nairobi, Kenya.**

ABSTRACT

The main objective of the study was to assess factors affecting the effectiveness of supply chain management practices in Kenyan public sector case of Ministry of Finance with the aim of assessing the effect of supplier relationship on the effectiveness of supply chain management practices. The study adopted a descriptive case research design with study population of 120 management staff working at the Ministry of Finance's procurement, finance and administration departments from which a sample size of 60 respondents was drawn. Questionnaires were used for data collection and descriptive statistics data analysis method was applied to analyze data aided by Statistical Package for Social Sciences. The study identified that lack of supplier relationship management strategies lowered the effectiveness of supply chain management functions. The study recommended application of supplier collaboration strategies.

KEYWORDS

Procurement, Supplier and Customer Relationship, Supply Chain Management

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/papers/6115ijmvsc03.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/vol6.html>

REFERENCES

- 1 Abraham k.(2009).
Managing Human Resources, Fourth Edition, Prentice Hall
- 2 Ansari s.(2009). Purchasing and Supply Management, 6th edition, McGraw-Hill
- 3 Athur, P.(2007). "Supply chain management", Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science, Vol. 38
- 4 Armstrong.(2010). Human resource management. Third edition. Kogan Page. USA. Washington,
- 5 Baden, L.(2004). "Supply chain management", Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science, Vol. 28
- 6 Bill, L.(2009). Supplier Management. Third Edition; Pearson Publisher
- 7 Boyer, S.(2010). "Research opportunities in supply chain management", Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science, Vol. 38
- 8 Bogdan, J.(2003). Understanding Conceptual Framework; Second edition. Kogan Page Publishers
- 9 Bowersok, P.(2000). Purchasing and Supply Management, 6th edition, McGraw-Hill.
- 10 Braxton, P.(2008). Supply Chain Management, 4th edition, McGraw-Hill. UK. London
- 11 Bren, M.(2009). European Logistics: Markets, Management and Strategy. First Edition. Blackwell. Oxford, London
- 12 Browne, M.(2004). European Logistics: Markets, Management and Strategy. First Edition. Blackwell. Oxford,
- 13 Clerk, S.(2003). "Supply chain management", Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science, Vol. 38
- 14 Cooper, J.(2004). Supply Chain Management Practices. Second Edition. Pearson Publishers
- 15 Cooper, R.D., & Schindler, P.(2003). Business Research Methods. Third Edition. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- 16 Coote, B.(2002). The Trade Trap: Poverty and Global Commodity Markets, Oxfam, Oxford.
- 17 Cox, C. (2003), Chocolate Unwrapped: The Politics of Pleasure, The Women's Environmental Network, London.
- 18 Coellho, A.(2003). Channel performance in single vs multiple channel strategies, International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management, Vol. 31
- 19 Caines, C.(2005). Implementation of supply chain management and its impact on the Value of firms", Supply Chain Management: An International Journal, Vol. 10
- 20 Cravens, C.(2006). "Supply chain management and its impact on the Value of firms", Supply Chain Management: An International Journal, Vol. 22
- 21 Dempsey, B.(2003). Research Methods, Fourth Edition, Pearson Publishers
- 22 Easingwood, G.(2007). Supplier Management. Third Edition; Pearson Publisher
- 23 Emberson, C. (2006). Supply chain management. Supply Chain Management Journal, Vol. 32
- 24 Edward, C.(2008). Supply Chain Management International Journal, Vol. 44
- 25 Cravens, C.(2006). "Supply chain management and its impact on the Value of firms", Supply Chain Management: An International Journal, Vol. 22

The Influence of Individual Factors on The Entrepreneurial Intention

AmariFaroukand AbbasIkramand BoudabbousSami

Management,UniversityofSfax,FSEGS3018 Sfax,Tunisia.

ABSTRACT

Today, no one is safe from forces and pressures, which are exerted on it, because of asignificant number of the requirements in particular as regards competitiveness, the needfor change, or the crises and the deregulations. In front of the economic and socialturbulences which we know, the creation of new company appears as a cause of generalinterest. This research papers focuses on the problematic of the entrepreneurship, andmore particularly on the stake which this domain represents in our society, by treating the determinants of the entrepreneurial intention. To face this news gives, students mustreconsidertheirbehaviors andtheirpracticestorenew themselves,toopenoutandreinforce their position in the market. Some of these practices form what one calls theentrepreneurial orientation. For this reason, we will devote this paper for better encirclingandapprehendingtheconceptofindividualfactors,andwetriedtoknowhowtheindividual factors (motivations, need for accomplishment, need for autonomy, passion todevelop its own idea, individual characteristics, work experience, teaching) can influence theintentionoftheentrepreneur tocreatehisownproject.Wefocusedonreviewliterature through a survey of a sample of students from the Higher Institute of BusinessAdministrationofSfax(Tunisia).

KEYWORDS

individual factors, motivational, need for achievement, need for autonomy, passion todevelopitsownidea,individualcharacteristics,workexperience,teaching, intention.

ForMoreDetails:<http://airccse.org/journal/myvc/papers/5414ijmyvc04.pdf>

VolumeLink:<http://airccse.org/journal/myvc/vol5.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Moreau R (2004), « émergence organisationnelle: Le cas des entreprises de nouvelles technologies », Thèse de doctorat en Sociologie, Université de Nantes.
- [2] Baccari E., (2006), « Les motivations entrepreneuriales des jeunes entrepreneurs tunisiens : étude exploratoire », L'internationalisation des PME et ses conséquences sur les stratégies entrepreneuriales, 8ème Congrès International Francophone sur la PME, 25-26-27 octobre, Haute école de gestion (HEG), Fribourg, Suisse.
- [3] Alain Fayolle et Benoît Gailly (2009), Évaluation d'une formation en entrepreneuriat: prédisposition et impacts sur l'intention d'entreprendre *M@n@gement*, 12(3), 176-203.
- [4] Shaper A. et al (1982), The social dimensions of entrepreneurship, *Encyclopedia of entrepreneurship*, Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall, chap. IV, IV (1982), pp. 72-90.
- [5] Gergen M.-M., Jurtas S (1992), *Psychologie sociale*, Editions Etudes Vivantes, Québec, 551 pages.
- [6] Clelland (1965), "Achievement and entrepreneurship: A longitudinal study", *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 1, p. 389-392.
- [7] Janssen, F. (2006). *Entreprendre: Une introduction à l'entrepreneuriat*.
- [8] Davidsson, P (1995), "Determinants of entrepreneurial intentions", *RENTIX Workshop*, Piacenza, Italy, nov. 23-24.
- [9] Boissin, J.-P., Chollet, B. et Emin, S (2009), Les déterminants de l'intention de créer une entreprise chez les étudiants : un test empirique, *M@n@gement*, vol. 12, n°1, p. 28-51.
- [10] Ajzen, I. (1991), « The Theory of Planned Behaviour ». *Organizational Behavior*, 179-211.
- [11] Begley (1987), T. Psychological characteristics associated with performance in entrepreneurial firms and smaller businesses. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 2(1), 79-93.
- [12] Gianneloni J.-L., Vernet E (1995), *Etudes de marché*, Paris, Edition Vuibert, 482 pages.
- [13] Evrard, Y (2003), *Market : Etudes et recherches en marketing*, 3ème Edition, Paris, Dunod.